

GAS TRANSPORT IN PREPREGS: MODEL AND PERMEABILITY EXPERIMENTS

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SUMMARY

Vacuum evacuation of trapped gas and volatiles is an important mechanism for void management in composites processing. This paper presents a mathematical model for gas transport in composites laminates as well as gas permeability tests, in-plane and through-thickness, for Toray T800H/3900-2 tape and fabric prepregs.

Keywords: Porosity, Voids, Permeability, Processing, Quality

INTRODUCTION

Controlling voids and porosity is important when processing composite structures [1] as they have a negative effect on mechanical and physical properties of a laminate [2,3]. In aerospace applications there is often an upper limit on the amount of porosity allowed to ensure that the laminate meets strength specifications. The amount of voids in a laminate is governed by the interaction of many factors including: type of prepreg (chemistry, tack, fibre architecture, morphology), ply orientation, ply terminations, lay-up method, debulking, laminate size and shape, detailed geometry (curvature and radii), tooling (male or female), bagging details, and process cycle (temperature, vacuum, and pressure). Although there are several theories in the literature about individual phenomena such void growth and dissolution, the subject is complex and not yet fully understood.

Void management can be achieved by controlling mechanisms that generates voids, void sources, and mechanisms that remove or mitigate voids, void sinks. Void sources include air trapped within and between plies during lay-up, volatiles given off by the resin during processing, and potential tool and bag leaks during cure. Void sinks include vacuum evacuation of the laminate and hydrostatic resin pressure during cure. The effectiveness of the void sources and void sinks are dependent on the detailed process conditions. A simple void management strategy is to minimize void sources and maximize void sinks, e.g. keep gas evacuation paths open and apply vacuum until trapped air and volatiles are evacuated to the maximum extent; close gas evacuation paths (through resin flow) and generate maximum resin hydrostatic pressure to keep remaining volatiles in solution as well as reduce the size of any voids with trapped air.

There is a body of work in the area of void growth and dissolution in composites processing and there are fairly well established theories regarding the resin pressure required to keep volatiles in solution, e.g. [4-8]. The void growth and dissolution work originated with a focus on surface bleeding prepreg systems and was later applied to no-bleed net resin systems, and out-of-autoclave prepreg systems. Removal of air and

volatiles through vacuum evacuation has received less attention, but there has been work done with regards to permeability and a gas transport in preregs [9-11]. With net resin system that are not designed for surface bleeding, and for out-of-autoclave (OOA) preregs in particular, vacuum evacuation of trapped air and volatiles becomes an important, if not the dominant, mechanism available for void management.

This paper presents a mathematical model for one-dimensional gas transport in composites laminates based on Darcy flow and the ideal gas law. A simple closed-form expression for the mass fraction of gas removed as a function of time is developed as well as general scaling laws for gas evacuation in laminates. The paper also presents permeability experiments and permeability data for Toray CFRP unidirectional tape (T800SC-24000-10E/3900-28) and fabric laminates (T800H-6K PW/3900-20), in-plane and through-thickness.

GAS TRANSPORT MODEL

Consider one-dimensional gas transport through a gas permeable medium (Figure 1). The medium can either be an uncured prepreg, a breather, or any other medium that allows for gas transport in composites processing. We assume that there are gas channels, or an inter-connected “vascular network”, that allows gas to permeate through the medium.

Figure 1. Schematic of the 1D gas transport problem.

Continuity gives

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\rho \cdot v) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where ρ = density [kg/m³], v = velocity [m/s], t = time [s], and x = distance [m]. Assuming Darcy flow of gas through the medium

$$v = -\frac{K}{\mu} \frac{dp}{dx} \quad (2)$$

where K = permeability [m²], μ = dynamic viscosity [Pa·s], and p = pressure [Pa]. If the gas is treated as an ideal gas

$$pV = nRT \quad \text{or} \quad p = \rho \cdot \frac{RT}{M} \quad (3)$$

where V = volume [m^3], n = number of moles of gas [mol], R = universal gas constant [$\text{J}/(\text{mol}\cdot\text{K})$], T = temperature [K], and M = molar mass [kg/mol]. Equations (1-3) give the following differential equation for the gas pressure $p(x,t)$:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} - \frac{K}{\mu} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(p \cdot \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \right) = 0 \quad (4)$$

if it is assumed that neither K , μ , nor T are a function of x .

The steady-state solution of eq. (4) gives the volumetric flow $Q(\text{m}^3/\text{s})$ and pressure distribution $p(x)$ along a laminate where one end sees a pressure $p(x=0)=p_0$ and the other $p(x=L)=p_L$, see Figure 1. The volumetric flow at $x=0$, $Q(x=0)=Q_0$, and $x=L$, $Q(x=L)=Q_L$, and the pressure distribution along the laminate $p(x)$ are given by:

$$Q_0 = \frac{AK}{2\mu L} \left(\frac{p_0^2 - p_L^2}{p_0} \right); \quad Q_L = \frac{AK}{2\mu L} \left(\frac{p_0^2 - p_L^2}{p_L} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$p(x) = \sqrt{\frac{x}{L} (p_L^2 - p_0^2) + p_0^2} \quad (6)$$

where A and L are the cross-sectional area and the length of the laminate, respectively.

To solve eq. (5) in the general case we nondimensionalize the equation with respect to time and distance as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial p^*}{\partial \tau} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \left(p^* \cdot \frac{\partial p^*}{\partial \xi} \right) &= 0; \quad \text{where} \\ \xi &= \frac{x}{L}; \quad p^* = \frac{p}{p_0}; \quad \tau = \frac{Kp_0}{\mu L^2} t \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where ξ is nondimensional distance, p^* is nondimensional pressure, and τ is nondimensional time. The nondimensional factors in equation (7) give some interesting scaling laws for gas evacuation. For example, the time t it takes to reach a new pressure state is proportional to the viscosity of the gas, μ , the length of the laminate squared, L^2 , and is inversely proportional to the initial pressure p_0 and the permeability of the medium K . Thus a laminate with twice the permeability will evacuate twice as fast, and

a laminate with twice the distance to the vacuum system will take four times longer to evacuate.

We can now analyze one-dimensional gas evacuation of a laminate. The whole laminate is initially at pressure p_0 (ambient pressure) and vacuum pressure $p_V = p_L$ is applied at $x=L$ at time $t=0$. The volume of gas in the laminate is assumed fixed and the vacuum applied at $x=L$ evacuates the gas from the laminate via Darcy flow. In this case, eq. (7) needs to be solved for the following boundary condition

$$\left. \frac{\partial p^*}{\partial \xi} \right|_{\xi=0} = 0, \quad p^*(1, \tau) = p_V \quad (8)$$

Equation (7) with boundary conditions (8) has no known analytic solution and was solved numerically using the Mathematica software. The numerical solution was used to develop an approximate general expression for the amount of gas removed as a function of time during gas evacuation. The ideal gas law, eq. (3), gives that the mass of gas is proportional to the pressure as the volume of the vascular network gas is assumed fixed.

By integrating the pressure distribution along the length of the laminate at different times, the mass of gas remaining in the prepreg as a function of time was calculated and the following simple equation for the mass fraction of gas remaining m/m_0 as a function of dimensionless time τ is obtained

$$\frac{m}{m_0} \approx e^{-0.9\tau^{0.6}} \quad (9)$$

By determining the dimensionless time τ it takes to reach a specific fraction of gas remaining m/m_0 from eq. (9), the actual time t can be calculated based on the length L , permeability K , initial pressure p_0 , and viscosity μ of the gas using the relationship between t and τ in eq. (7).

PERMEABILITY TESTING

One of the key parameters affecting gas transport is the permeability K of the medium. The permeability of a laminate during vacuum evacuation can be determined from a steady-state test by measuring the gas pressures on the atmospheric and vacuum sides, p_0 and p_L , as well as the air flow on the atmospheric side, Q_0 (Figure 1). This information together with the cross-sectional area A , the length of the laminate in the direction of the flow L , allows the permeability K to be calculated from eq. (5).

The experimental set-up used to measure in-plane permeability was based on the work by Seferis et al. [9,10] (Figure 2). The standard length and width of the samples tested were $L = 51$ mm, $W = 101.6$ mm. To ensure that there was no unwanted gas transport during the test, the laminate was bagged with three separate, isolated, compartments. The right compartment was used to apply vacuum to the laminate, and the left compartment was used to expose the left end of the laminate to atmospheric pressure

and to measure the volumetric gas flow with a high accuracy shielded Rotameter (Omega® Engineering). The middle compartment contains the laminate, which is covered on all sides with sealant tape (AT-200Y, Airtech advanced materials group), except on the cross-section through which gas is flowing.

Laminates were made with different lay-ups using Toray CFRP unidirectional tape (T800SC-24000-10E/3900-28) and fabric (T800H-6K PW/3900-20) prepreps. The prepreg was laid-up on a steel tool followed by vacuum debulking for 5 minutes after each layer. When the lay-up and debulking was finished, the sample edges were trimmed to size with a sharp knife.

Figure 2. Test set-up for in-plane permeability testing. A) Top view; B) Side view.

After laminates were laid-up, debulked, and bagged, the overall bagging system was checked for leaks by applying full vacuum in all three compartments (min 29.5 in Hg). After achieving full vacuum, the vacuum valves were closed and the gauge pressures were monitored for 10 minutes in all compartments to ensure there were no observable leaks. If leaks were detected, the bagging system was carefully examined and adjusted. After this, the set-up was checked for inter-compartmental leaks by applying full vacuum to the middle compartment only. After achieving full vacuum, the valve was closed and the change in gauge pressure with time was observed to detect any leaks into the middle compartment through the sealant tape from the left and right compartments. After the laminate passed both of these vacuum checks, permeability testing was conducted.

Permeability tests were performed as follows. First, vacuum was applied to all compartments. After achieving full vacuum, the vacuum port in the left compartment

was opened to atmosphere via a volumetric flow meter. After a few minutes, the flow reached steady state conditions and the flow rate and gauge vacuum pressure were measured and permeability was calculated using eq. (5).

The experimental set-up used to measure through-thickness permeability is shown in Figure 3. The sample was sealed around the edges with soft silicon rubber sheets (2 mm thick) to prevent air flow out of the laminate in the in-plane direction. The top and bottom silicon rubber sheets as well as the steel plates had a circular hole of 1 inch diameter that determined the effective flow area. Similar to the in-plane experiments, the samples were debulked for 5 minutes after each layer and the edges were trimmed with a sharp knife to achieve a good seal with the silicon rubber. The gas integrity of the system was tested by placing a thin gas impermeable Teflon sheet between the sample and steel mesh. The measured air flow was below the measurement sensitivity of the flow meters with the impermeable Teflon sheet in place, indicating that the set-up was free of leaks. After passing the leak check, the volumetric gas flow was measured using the same equipment and procedures as for the in-plane tests.

Figure 3. Test set-up for in-plane permeability testing. A) Top view; B) Side view.

PERMEABILITY RESULTS

Permeability tests were performed to study the effect of laminate lay-up, prepreg type, and flow direction (in-plane and through-thickness), on air permeability. Each test was repeated three times. Note that all permeability results are presented in the units (μm^2),

which equals $10^{-12}(\text{m}^2)$. Figure 4 shows the measured in-plane permeability of tape laminates with different lay-ups.

Figure 4. In-plane permeability of tape laminates with different lay-ups (Toray T800SC-24000-10E/3900-28). Solid bars represent the average permeabilities and error bars one standard deviation.

Figure 4 shows that the in-plane permeability of the tape material is highest in the fibre direction, which is an order of magnitude higher than in the transverse (90) direction. The 0/90 laminate has a permeability that is approximately the weighted average of the permeability in the fibre and transverse directions. There is therefore a strong preference for gas to permeate in the fibre direction of the tape material.

In-plane permeability test of 8 ply fabric laminates gave a permeability of $5.49 \cdot 10^{-1} \pm 5.69 \cdot 10^{-2} (\mu\text{m}^2)$, which is more than 25 times higher than the permeability of the tape material in the fibre direction.

To put the measured in-plane permeabilities in context, in-plane permeability testing of 10oz breather cloth (Airweave® N10, Airtech advanced materials group) gave a permeability value of $K = 273 \pm 26 (\mu\text{m}^2)$, which is three and four orders of magnitude higher than for the fabric and tape prepreg laminates, respectively.

Through-thickness permeability testing of tape laminates gave no measurable gas flow. Given the resolution of the flow meters, the through-thickness permeability of the tape was less than $1 \cdot 10^{-4} (\mu\text{m}^2)$, which is two orders of magnitude less than the in-plane permeability in the fibre direction for the same prepreg.

Through-thickness permeability testing of 8 ply fabric laminates gave a permeability of $3.52 \cdot 10^{-3} \pm 8.24 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (μm^2), which is very low and close to the transverse permeability of the tape material. Table 1 shows a summary of the relative measured permeabilities.

Table 1. Relative permeabilities of Toray T800H/3900-2 tape and fabric laminates.

Material and lay-up	Relative permeability
Tape (0) in-plane	1
Tape (90) in-plane	0.13
Tape (0/90) in-plane	0.47
Fabric (0) in-plane	27
Tape through-thickness	< 0.01
Fabric through-thickness	0.17

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The large differences in gas permeability of uncured preregs means that in real laminates with varying thickness, complex geometry, and perhaps a combination of tape and fabric prepreg, gas flow to the vacuum system is strongly anisotropic and the direction of flow varies ply by ply. Virtually no gas will flow in the thickness direction of the laminate and gas flow will preferentially follow the fibre direction of the individual plies. The permeability results can qualitatively guide the design of the bagging and vacuum system to ensure that all regions of the laminate have a non-obstructed high permeability evacuation path all the way to the vacuum system.

By combining the permeability results with the mathematical model developed for gas evacuation, quantitative guidelines for the required debulking time can be established. Equations (7) and (9) give the time t required to reach a mass fraction of gas remaining in the laminate m/m_0 as a function of the ratio of the length of the laminate squared L^2 to the permeability K

$$t = \frac{\mu}{p_0} \frac{L^2}{K} \left[-\frac{1}{0.9} \ln \left(\frac{m}{m_0} \right) \right]^{0.6} \quad (10)$$

For example, for a 1 m long laminate made of the fabric prepreg tested in this study, the time required to remove 90% of the gas trapped during lay-up ($m/m_0 = 10\%$) is approximately 36 minutes, whereas it only takes 5 minutes to remove 50% of the air for the same laminate. To achieve 90% gas removal from a tape laminate that is 4 m long, the debulking time has to be approximately 11,500 minutes, or over 7 days.

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